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Scenarios for threats from pests and diseases in the arable and horticulture sector in Scotland.

Final Report

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Contributors and research team

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Executive Summary

The future sustainability of agricultural production in Scotland and globally is under pressure from environmental stresses (such as climate change, soil degradation, pest and diseases) and influenced by economic and political factors.

Pests and diseases can cause important economic losses in the agricultural sector with devastating social consequences as well as threats to food security. The cereal, fruit and potato sectors, valued at over £1 billion in 2019 according to Scottish Government statistics, contribute significantly to the Scottish economy. However, between 15% and 20% of the crops are lost to pests and diseases annually with an economic value loss of close to £200 million (Plant Health Centre, 2024).

In this study, by applying a co-designed scenario planning methodology, in collaboration with stakeholders from farming, agronomy, regulation, research and policy, we developed plausible accounts to explore future possibilities regarding effects of pests and diseases and mitigation options in the arable and horticulture sector.

By looking at past and present events, this scenario exercise aimed to identify avenues which are robust, flexible but imperfect guides to unpredictable future events and prepare for and prevent future threats. We conducted two one-day in-person workshops in June and September 2023, two half-day online workshops in December 2023 and one webinar in April 2024 with balanced representation of stakeholders from the arable and horticulture sector in Scotland.

Through the workshops, 4 plausible scenarios were developed - based on varying hypotheses of what global and national climate, economy and politics might look like in a 10-year horizon and how these could affect the sector. The 4 scenarios were assessed for the likely impacts on the sector of 3 pests and diseases identified from other work as likely increasing threats to production: Colorado potato beetle, Blueberry rust and Wheat stem rust.

This served as the basis for stakeholders to draw out recommendations for adaptation of the sector and mitigation against pest and disease threats. Across the 4 scenarios, stakeholders concurred that the following was crucial for the future of the sector: a better understanding of chemical and **biological control products** and the **government enabling** adaptation through various mechanisms such as support schemes, market regulation, changes in performance metrics, inclusion of grassroots movements' input, and investing in infrastructure, supported by **research and development**. Finally, **diversification was discussed** as it may either increase resilience to pests and disease and/or increase the availability of host plant species for pest and pathogens.

Stakeholders' recommendations.

Policy and regulation

- Consider invasive plant pests and pathogens as agricultural support programmes are developed (e.g. government assurance to buffer losses)
- Promote crop production for food rather than non-food uses
- Improve border controls and inspections to reduce the risks of crop losses and pest and disease controls
- Increase support for farmers to monitor fields in relation to plant pests and pathogens
- Improve consumer education on the impact of their food choices;
- Ensure fairer market returns to growers to allow investment in (more expensive) production costs and to monitor and reward system performance.

Farming

- Adopt existing solutions, such as detection and application, in good time to mitigate pest and disease impacts
- Switch from monocultures to a more diverse cropping system, including resistant varieties and mixtures of landraces, to increase resilience

Research

- Conduct research and development on adapting the farming calendar for planting to the changing climate
- Conduct research and development on agrobiodiversity to provide buffers against potential threats
- Improve weather-driven crop pest and pathogen risk models (“decision support systems”) to enable targeted control measures
- Analyse the cost implications of changing pest and disease management (e.g. switching from chemical to biological/novel controls)

Introduction

Plant health is essential for humanity as it provides food, oxygen but also benefits to well-being, such as biodiversity. Globalisation, climate and environmental change are adding pressure to plant health as they increase the risks of pests and diseases. Pests and diseases can cause important economic losses in the agricultural sector with devastating social consequences as well as threats to food security.

During the 1840s, potato harvests failed repeatedly due to the blight (*Phytophthora infestans*). The Great Famine this caused in Ireland, compounded by prevailing agricultural policies and limited famine relief, had severe and long-lasting impacts on demographics, emigration, culture and the shaping of societies both in North Western Europe and in the Americas (O'Rourke, 1994).

Likewise, the devastating coffee leaf rust fungus (*Hemileia vastatrix*) introduced to Sri Lanka from West Africa in the 1860s led to a ten-year economic crisis, the demise of what was once the world's third largest coffee export industry (McCook, 2006) and a dramatic socio-economic transformation of Ceylonese society (Wenzlhuemer, 2008). It provoked drastic changes in global commodity trade and British consumption habits shifting from heavy coffee consumption to tea (Gullino, 2021).

More recently and nowadays, global climate change can affect agricultural production and "food security around the world beyond changes in crop prices and social welfare. So rigorous pest control and damage predictions are needed" (Han, et al., 2023). Assessments of the potential risks of pests and diseases exist, however monitoring cannot be achieved only through the means of technological improvements (Hasan, Nusrat et al. 2023). More involvement of various stakeholders in this process is also needed to improve the assessment of farming sustainability in general (Chopin, et al. 2021) and pest and disease biosecurity risks in particular (Duong, et al. 2019).

In response to this need and recognising stakeholders' knowledge and potential to help in identifying risks, and developing preventative actions to control plant pests and diseases, we used scenario planning methodology to develop plausible scenarios with stakeholders for arable and horticulture pests and pathogens in Scotland.

The cereal, fruit and potato sectors, valued at over £1 billion in 2019 according to Scottish Government statistics, contribute significantly to the Scottish economy. The future sustainability of agricultural production in Scotland and globally is under pressure from environmental stresses (soil degradation, pest and diseases, climate change) and influenced by economic and political factors.

The overall aim of this research was to work with agricultural stakeholders to explore what might happen to arable and horticulture production in Scotland in the future and by doing so, raise awareness, stimulate creative thinking, and gain insights about the interactions between the social, economic and environmental drivers of change.

Through plausible accounts we explored future possibilities with stakeholders rather than making forecasts. By looking at past and present events, this exercise aimed to identify avenues which are robust, flexible but imperfect guides to unpredictable future events and prepare for and prevent future threats.

The objectives of the research were to:

- i) Characterise key threats to the sustainability of the Scottish arable and horticulture sector;
- ii) Co-design plausible future scenarios with stakeholders;
- iii) Elicit stakeholders' knowledge about likely future pest and pathogen issues;

- iv) Test scenario resilience to specific pests and pathogens and identify solutions (technology, regulatory, knowledge) for safeguarding the cereal, fruit and potato sectors against future pest and disease risks; and
- v) Transfer knowledge to plant-health experts and issue practical guidance for growers.

The first objective (completed in March 2023; Lozada & Karley, 2023) involved working with stakeholders to characterise and prioritise key threats to the sustainability of the Scottish arable and horticulture sector. Information was gathered using an online survey distributed to agricultural stakeholders (farmers, agronomists, crop breeders, scientists, policy advisors, regulatory bodies, and value chain actors) supplemented by face-to-face discussion groups at relevant stakeholder events.

The second, third and fourth objectives involve developing plausible scenarios with stakeholders in the cereal, fruit and potato sectors and analysing these scenarios to identify mitigating actions. Through a series of workshops with stakeholders we achieved these objectives and also gathered additional insights into stakeholders’ perceptions of future pest and disease threats to Scottish agriculture.

Arable and horticultural sector in Scotland.

Agriculture accounts for 69% (5.33 million hectares) of the total Scottish land area (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2023) of which around 10 % is used to grow arable crops, such as cereals, fruit and vegetables (Scottish Government, 2021).

Figure 1. Map of Scotland showing main farming types in each area (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2023)

In 2021, there were 13,253 arable farm holdings (crops and fallow) covering 588,801 hectares. Most of the arable land was used for cereal growing (73% of arable land) while horticultural crops accounted for a small proportion (9% of arable land).

In 2019, Scottish farmers produced around 6.55 million tons of arable and horticultural produce (Scottish Agriculture Tables – economic report, 2020) where barley and wheat are the most important crops covering 85% of cropped land area and providing 87% and 50% respectively, of the needs of the whisky industry in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2021).

Regarding horticulture there was an increase of 7% in vegetables grown for human consumption in 2023 (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2023) compared with previous years.

Soft fruit growing area decreased by 7% in 2023 compared with previous years. Strawberries decreased by 11% but were

still the most popular soft growing fruit. This decline was seen across the UK. The land area used for raspberry has been declining since 2010. Increases in blackcurrant and blackberry were recorded in 2023 compared with previous years. Almost 70% of soft fruit are grown in poly-tunnels or glasshouses in Scotland.

Figure 2. Percentage of land in hectares under crops and horticultural for 2017-2021 mean (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2023).

The composition and amount of land grown under each crop is also important for the potential spread of pests and pathogens and interactions with host plants.

Decreases and increases of crops grown in spring and winter have been recorded due to reasons such as variation in crop prices and demand. In 2023, compared with the previous five-years' average, there was a 4% increase of winter crops and a 2% decrease in spring planting driven mainly by the 27% decrease in the area used to grow spring oats.

Alternating crops grown on a specific field each year following a planted pattern or sequence is called crop rotation and the permanence of one crop type in the same piece of land for several years is called continuous cropping. The practice of each of these could also influence pest and disease dynamics. In Scotland 85% of the holdings with arable land had at least 75% or more land in crop rotation covering 562,700 hectares (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2023).

In terms of value to the Scottish economy, the combined arable and horticultural output was around £1.1 billion (in 2019), with approx. one-third attributable to cereals (£408 M), one-quarter to potatoes (£250 M) and 13% to fruit crops (£144 M). The potato seed industry was valued at £100 million.

Regulation of plant pests and pathogens in Scotland

Plant health policy is fully devolved to the Scottish Parliament and Scottish Ministers are responsible for the response to any notifiable plant disease, although the assessment of plant pests and pathogens for potential invasion risk and impact considers the UK as a whole and is administrated by Defra's Plant Health Risk Register (PHRR). The EU plant health regimen set the bases of plant health controls in Scotland, and it is implemented through Scotland's Plant Health Regulations (2019).

In the first half of the 20th Century, over 100 new records of plant pathogenic viruses, bacteria and fungi were recorded in Scotland (Foister, 1961). Since then, 234 non-native pathogens - mainly fungi, with smaller numbers of oomycetes bacteria and viruses - were recorded as established in Great Britain between 1970 and 2004 (Jones and Baker, 2007). Slightly over half of these were found on ornamental crops, highlighting the importance of the live plant trade as a risk factor for plant disease import (Brasier, 2008).

Scotland has some of the highest yields and good quality crops in the world, but these conditions are also favourable for pest and pathogens. In 2022, as in 2020, 97% of arable crops received pesticide treatment. However, between 15% and 20% of the crops are lost to pest and disease damage annually with an economic loss of close to £200 million (PHC, 2024). These losses have a consequence for the whole agriculture sector, the economy and rural communities in Scotland.

Methods and scenario planning development.

Scenario planning in this research is a *set of narratives describing different alternative futures, constructed with an iterative approach based on the uncertainties of the context, with the aim to raise awareness of plausible futures and increase performance of the organizational* (Cordova-Pozo and Rouwette, 2023).

We co-designed scenarios with stakeholders following the methodology proposed in Duckett et al., (2022) and Boden et al., (2015) and EPIC (2014) for qualitative exploratory scenarios.

Our process integrates the six components identified by Cordova-Pozo and Rouwette (2023) in terms of being oriented to the future (1), concerning with external contexts (2) and following a narrative form (3); they are plausible (4) and part of a systematised set (5) of meaningfully different alternatives, raising awareness and increasing performance in the future based on the strategy adapted in the present (6).

In a co-design process, science and practice are equally important. The role of each is well defined, and both work together to co-develop the scenarios. In this process, scientists ensure the scientific soundness of the scenarios regarding the conceptual framework, methods and interpretation of results; and stakeholders provide specific regional knowledge which is the basis for developing the work. In our scenario building, stakeholders developed the narratives through a series of activities carefully thought by scientists and which are described below. Scientists also developed the contextual background for the scenarios.

To co-design the scenarios we ensure a balanced representation in the workshops of stakeholders from the arable and horticulture sector in Scotland. We recruited 16 participants representing

farmers, researchers, agro-industry organisations, and regulators. Detailed information about the recruitment strategy can be requested from the authors.

We conducted two one-day in-person workshops in June and September 2023, two half-day online workshops in December 2023 and one webinar in April 2024 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Activities carried out with stakeholders for scenario planning. P&D refers to Pest and Disease.

Scenario planning is the creation of plausible scenarios. The future, however, is unpredictable and uncertain. What we know is what has happened in the past and what is happening in the present. To develop the scenarios, we used existing knowledge to guide creative thinking to develop narratives for the future. This information helped stakeholders to identify drivers of change, critical uncertainties and their assumptions to finally develop the narratives. The scenarios were almost entirely developed by stakeholders and to achieve this aim we ensured that they had clear instructions and guidance to carry out each activity in the workshops. Figure 4 shows the activities followed in the workshops to develop the scenarios, discuss and analyse the scenarios, and make recommendations.

Figure 4. One-day in-person workshop activities carried out with stakeholders.

To develop the exploratory scenarios, we followed a focal question and used the five “STEEP” factors (Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental and Political) to comprehensively analyse past events, present processes and to construct plausible futures. Our focal question was:

“What will the Scottish arable and horticultural sector look like in 2033 and how resilient will it be to pests and disease?”

Review of past events. Using the same focal question and five set of colour coded post-its we asked participants about past events. The colour coding corresponded to each of the five factors of STEEP.

What ***has happened*** to the Scottish Arable and horticultural sector in the past X years and how resilient ***has it been*** to pests and disease?

Figure 5. Timeline developed by stakeholders, workshop in June 2023. The timeline from one of the scenario planning workshops where drivers of change were summarised for the previous 30 years. Sticky notes were colour-coded accordingly to the five factors of STEEP analysis.

Stakeholders highlighted various past events that have influenced the sector and its resilience to pests and diseases. The most frequently repeated events were related to:

- **Social:** Food; Dietary changes (obesity problems); Mobility of people; farm demographics
- **Technological:** Information; related innovations in land and food; and in innovations in plant pests and diseases control.
- **Economic:** Food system changes; economic damage to agricultural system by pests and diseases and weather events; also, opportunities.
- **Environmental:** Land use and management changes; pest and disease events and changes in rules and regulations; public awareness.
- **Political:** EU-CAP land policy trade-offs between biodiversity, net zero and food security; Brexit; State responses.

This process primed participants for the next step, which aimed to identify critical uncertainties for the agricultural sector using the five STEEP factors.

Figure 6. Drivers of Change identified by stakeholders at workshops.

Through the carousel method, participants were asked to agree collectively and select five critical uncertainties, one per STEEP category, for constructing the scenarios. Critical uncertainties refer to drivers that have major impact and the outcome is highly uncertain. With the selected critical uncertainties, participants were asked the **“what if” question** which helped them to develop the assumptions to build the morphological boxes. The morphological boxes were to describe the links between uncertainties in each STEEP category. These morphological boxes were used as the basis for drafting narratives of the exploratory scenarios.

The narratives for scenarios were developed by stakeholders in the two one-day in-person workshops. Four of these scenarios were expanded by the authors with further description and enhanced with additional contextual information in terms of new or anticipated policy developments, global events, sectoral developments etc.

A further two half-day online workshops were conducted with the same group of stakeholders (with 4 absences). The objective of these online workshops was to consult stakeholders on the scenario narratives, to test the scenario resilience to specific pests and pathogens, elicit stakeholders’ knowledge and awareness of pests and pathogens, and develop a set of recommendations to create a more resilient sector.

In the online workshop, the participants were asked to review and confirm or adjust the scenarios they had developed to ensure they were realistic and feasible.

Participants were also asked to list and discuss the pests and pathogens they anticipated becoming problematic in the future. The questions they responded to were:

1. Which pest and pathogens do you know?
2. What are their characteristics and behaviour?
3. How likely do you think these are to occur in Scotland in the next 10 years?

Afterwards, participants were presented with three pests/pathogens predicted to become more prevalent by modelling (Bebber, et al., 2024) which were: Colorado potato beetle, Blueberry rust; or identified as a potential threat by other research: Wheat stem rust (Figure 7) These three examples were chosen as representing threats to the dominant arable and horticultural crop types in Scotland (i.e. potato, cereal, soft fruit).

Colorado potato beetle

- Larvae and adults feed on several cultivated and wild members of the Solanaceae (potato, tomato, aubergine, and pepper)
- Each female can lay ~2000 eggs
- Feeding defoliates the plant causing up to 50% yield losses
- Can spread potato diseases (bacterial wilts)
- Outbreaks managed by crop/weed destruction (herbicide), insect eradication (insecticide) and soil/tuber incineration

Management:

- Biocontrol (natural enemies) is considered ineffective
- Chemical control using chlorpyrifos (no longer approved for use on potatoes in the UK) and thiacloprid
- GM (Bt toxin) effective but growers reluctant to use
- Resistance breeding lines derived from wild relatives (deterrent chemistry)
 - Resistance management necessary
- Cultural control using rotation, trapping and early planting to avoid second generation within one season

Colorado potato beetle: Warning after Hampshire discovery

The fully grown beetle is bright yellow or orange with black stripes

Not predicted:

Wheat stem rust appears to be re-invading the UK

- Recently re-emerged in Europe as environmental conditions have become more conducive (last epidemic was in 1955)
- Caused by the fungal pathogen *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*
- New supervirulent wheat stem rust isolates have emerged (Ug99 race group in Africa)
- Complex life cycle involving another host (barberry, *Berberis* spp.) which is increasingly grown in arable areas
 - can enhance the pathogen's genetic diversity and provide a seasonal bridge
- The disease can cause crop devastation
- Infected wheat plant found in southern UK in 2013
- Detected on barberry in a cereal hedgerow in 2017
- Only 20% of UK wheat varieties are resistant
- Good control relies on early application of rust-active azole fungicides (e.g. tebuconazole)

Blueberry rust

- Caused by the fungus *Thekopsora minima*
- Attacks a range of plants in the Ericaceae family
- Second host required to complete the life cycle (conifer, *Tsuga* species)
- Infection leads to premature leaf drop, reducing plant vigour, yield, and flower production the following year
- Predicted to have a serious impact on the commercial production of cultivated North American blueberry species from crop losses and increased pest control costs
- Potentially high environmental and social impact if *T. minima* attacks wild European *Vaccinium* species if this pest hybridised with the closely related native *Naohidemyces vaccinii* rust and led to a new virulent type (uncertain)

Management:

- Crop husbandry (pruning to increase air circulation and remove disease inoculum)
- Remove diseased plants
- No approved fungicides currently available in UK

Figure 7. Information about three selected pests/pathogens presented to stakeholders in the scenario testing online workshops.

To test the robustness of the future scenarios against predicted threats of pests and pathogens, participants were asked to imagine that each pest/pathogen threat is well established in Scotland in 2033 and answer the question 'How severely would your scenario be impacted?'. The responses were gathered by taking notes about what the outcomes would be in each scenario, and how severe the impact would be, using the following scale:

- Negligible/very minor (temporary) effect
- Small effect
- Moderate effect
- Major (long term) effect
- Permanent change

Finally, stakeholders were asked to recommend actions that could be taken now to mitigate the severity of the impact of these pests and diseases in the future for each of the scenarios.

In the final stage of this project, stakeholders were invited to attend a webinar and were presented with the results of the modelling and the scenarios. They had the opportunity to discuss the results and also were asked three questions:

1. What are your concerns for future pest and disease risks?
2. What further research is needed? (rank in priority order).
3. What is needed to make the arable/horticulture sector more resilient to pests and diseases? (rank in priority order)

In the final stage, we also gave the present report to stakeholders for feedback and editing.

Results

In the next section we will present the narratives of the four scenarios as well as the recommendations, stakeholders' knowledge elicitation and results from the consultation.

Scenario Planning

Exploratory scenarios are narratives for plausible futures. No one knows what might happen in the future and exploratory scenarios are simply tools to explore complexities which could develop in various forms. Exploratory scenarios are a vehicle to raise awareness of these complexities and tenable future developments.

The narratives presented below should be read as a tool to explore plausible future threats and opportunities in the arable and horticultural sector and its resilience to pests and diseases in a 10-year horizon.

Exploratory scenarios offer the opportunity to think creatively about the future and increase awareness of how the interaction between social and natural events could evolve in various ways into the future. The benefit of this process is to picture these plausible futures and think about recommendations that could work under various "futures". The recommendations are an important part of this methodology, and they are robust if they are relevant for all scenarios presented here. The robustness of the recommendation is valuable for policy makers as it is likely that the future could include some combination of different events elaborated in each of these scenarios.

Scenario 1

Crisis is opportunity for food security.

Society and government give the arable and horticulture sector priority and support. Declining international trade but increasing local market and local consumption allow for diversification and alternative production systems, increasing the opportunity for food security. Investment in regenerative/agroecological practices, technology and strong connection between consumption and production of food facilitates change.

This scenario takes place in a geopolitically unstable and crisis-ridden world (worsening of current trends).

A frozen conflict after Russia's aggression in Ukraine, and rising tensions between US and China, make for a dysfunctional international system, hampering effective climate action. Consequently, international trade reduces and forces a moderate increase of more separate regional trade blocks ('de-globalisation'). This is a less globalised world, which on the economic level seeks to build resilience against recessionary pressures, and on a political level undergoes increased divisiveness. The UK has a declining share of global trade including food trade and is increasingly exposed to harvest losses from a range of climate risks as climate becomes more chaotic within and across years.

On a political level society undergoes increased divisiveness. There are various, sometime diverging, societal and political trends. At the same time this ongoing crisis situation creates a conjuncture where civil society takes the opportunity to pressure governments for systemic changes. In the UK there is a push from a significant fraction of society for more climate action and awareness of the need for self-sufficiency and fairer distribution of profits.

Scotland diverges somewhat from the rest of the UK by stating that it was consulting and considering other options more formally during the mid-2020's as a result of pressure from civil society movements and consumer demands for environmentally friendly and healthy produce and for fair distribution of profits to farmers.

Successive Scottish governments failed to achieve the aim of reducing carbon emissions by 32% reductions by 2032 (as initially established in the 2021 Scotland Climate Smart Agriculture Framework) but some trends help the agricultural sector to move towards the Net Zero target.

Scotland steers towards an alternative path. Within the economy, the agriculture sector gets priority and farmers are supported (for learning) and incentivised (to reduce risks) to find ways to increase farm resilience, including through cooperation with other farmers and the adoption of more regenerative practices (hedging their bets). With the international context, input prices and costs of production become very high and the preferred option is the use of organic and other management options which allow for significant less reliance on synthetic fertilizers.

Under pressure from part of society, Scotland now considers the long-established work by civil society and grass roots organisations such as Food Farming and Countryside Commission, Soils Association Scotland, and Nourish Scotland as high-potential alternatives and follows their lead in the sense of seeking less intensive production, more diversification of crops, pressure to regulate markets to change the standards of production demanded of farmers, and more equitable prices and risk sharing. Bringing risk to the fore including the distribution of benefits and burdens is reflected in the pull from markets including insurance policies and nature and climate disclosures.

The government is also ready to collaborate with farmers regarding innovation by lessening the administrative barriers to market effective biocontrol and bioproducts, facilitating a move towards an alternative arable and horticultural production system. Based

on risk- management and clarity of ‘who pays when it all goes wrong’, this creates the right conditions that guarantee better prices for farmers and help in the creation of alternative local markets and effective subsidies structure.

Within the strategies taken, demand management and behaviour change are central. Supporting this is an increased investment in technology, which plays an important role with more research carried out and better understanding about technological tools (e.g Gene Editing) by society and decision makers. Spreading bets and managing for multiple benefits and cascading risks help the sector to be more resilient and for agriculture to progress towards Net Zero although without achieving policy goals. Gene editing is allowed also in Scotland and this leads to the development of more pest resistant crops and reduces the use of pesticides. In Scotland, the pressure from civil society movements and consumer demands for environmentally friendly and healthy produce and for fair distribution of profits to farmers begins to translate into policy through both the market and a subsidy structure created after CAP replacement and the Good Food Nation Act (via the markets). This helps in the creation of alternative local markets and effective subsidies structure for locally produced food.

Colorado Potato Beetle	Wheat Stem Rust	Blueberry Rust
Major (long term) effect.	Moderate effect.	Moderate effect.
<p>At present, Scotland can only implement voluntary measures for CPB control as the rules and regulations for importing plants and seeds are carried out by DEFRA (UK).</p> <p>Pest control measures for Scotland are easy to carry out at early stages of CPB infestation. Once the CPB is established it is very difficult to control without the use of effective chemistries for insect control.</p> <p>Diversification could also increase threats to arable and horticultural production because it could lead to more host plant for CPB.</p>	<p>With only 20 % of wheat varieties showing resistance, this pathogen could devastate a cereal crop.</p> <p>Again, if appropriate chemistry is available the risks could potentially be reduced.</p> <p>Climate change also could potentially increase the risks of pest dispersion.</p> <p>With the use of fungicides, the impact would be less.</p> <p>Control of this pathogen will be dependent upon increasing availability of effective biological pest control products.</p>	<p>Blueberries are grown in tunnels. If there is a disease on top of lack of competitive prices it would become very difficult to continue producing the crop. How can the fruit sector be sustainable?</p> <p>Once the disease is in the country it is very difficult to get rid of.</p> <p>Improving husbandry practices is recommended.</p> <p>Increasing forest area, especially conifers cover in Scotland, could increase the risk of this disease as several woody species act as a secondary host.</p>

Recommendations by stakeholders.

- Reduce bureaucratic processes and regulatory barriers for development of effective biocontrol products.
- Consolidation of all different insurance schemes that companies need for their agendas of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) such as Red Tractor, LEAF marque etc. This will reduce overlapping and competition between schemes but also lessen risk, work and costs to farmers (for instance through primary registration)
- Value better the environment that Scotland has. Use it as a marketing opportunity.
- Recognition that agricultural systems have evolved over decades to reflect demands from consumers and manufacturing sectors, and delivering Government duties about drinking water and affordable food. But the distribution and ownership of risk in this system remains unclear and the costs are, ultimately, borne by the Government/taxpayer (while a small number of people benefit).
- Support for infrastructure. Need to improve infrastructure for farming for more productive land. If you want more productive land, there is a need to support infrastructure (e.g. installing field drainage is currently left to individual farmers).
- Demand management and behaviour change.

Scotland's own vision

International trade continues to increase. The arable and horticulture sector are prepared for producing more for international markets. Scotland increases its level of autonomy which allows for implementation of its own vision for trade leading to a consolidated and growing arable and horticulture sector. Investment in technology and research and development help to mitigate external shocks. People are more connected to food provenance.

The world continues to be unstable politically and economically (extension of current trends). However, with Russia's war on Ukraine ended and an easing of geopolitical tensions between China and the US, the global economy overall maintains a path towards free trade although adapting to some new protectionist tendencies.

The UK continues to increase its international trade with other countries and improves its economic and political relations globally. Grain exports from Ukraine and Russia return to patterns roughly similar to the pre-2022 patterns, which renders acceptable the UK's continued dependence on imports for a significant proportion of its food.

The UK manages to keep out of international conflicts and crises but internal political instability adds to the country's fragmentation.

In this context Scotland manages to agree with the rest of the UK to have a higher degree of devolution, a moderate economic autonomy (including less dependence on the UK food-system supply chain) and gets closer to the EU approach of more protection through environmental and quality standards. Exports and imports of an important proportion of Scottish products allows stability and room for planning, improving and protecting the agriculture sector. Scotland could voluntarily introduce restrictions on some practices. This divergence between Scotland and the rest of the UK presents both threats and opportunities.

Following the UK's withdrawal from the EU and the conclusion of the Trade and Cooperation agreement in 2021, Scotland develops and achieves to a certain degree its own vision for trade. Scotland does so by applying its five principles of inclusive growth, well-being, sustainability and 'just transition' to net zero, and good governance to Scotland's economy, Scotland's People, and the planet.

Successive Scottish governments achieve the aim of reducing carbon emissions by 32% by 2032 (as initially established in the 2021 Scotland Climate Smart Agriculture Framework).

Scotland achieves moderate autonomy from the UK agro-food supply chain and, therefore, is able to implement some limited restrictions, having external control and avoiding dynamics of a "race-to-the-bottom" between nations. The UK devolves to Scotland a limited number of trade agreements with the EU, which warrants a degree of economic stability and allows the farming industry to maintain and promote good practices. This divergence between Scotland and the rest of the UK presents both threats and opportunities. Scotland voluntarily introduces some restrictions on certain practices. Scottish producers receive fairer market returns, enabling them to invest in research and development and in newer and potentially more expensive practices that make production more resilient (and reduces the externalisation of costs). The farming industry remains in good shape allowing new entrants and more diversified (size and demographics) arable and horticultural farms with variation of farm sizes. The horticulture sector recovers from the decline it experienced in the early 2020s.

Weather becomes more unpredictable, but warmer and wetter, affecting different parts of the industry differently each year, with significant harvest losses arising from extreme events and unusual patterns of weather in addition to an array of pests, pathogens and disease. In Scotland, the Government develops a programme to establish precision and targeted farming practices, which is adopted by much of the sector, allowing the industry to adapt and mitigate some of the shocks and allowing strategies to be implemented that protect the sector from stronger shocks. Controlled use of pesticides prevents resistance from developing in plant pests and pathogens. New crops and crop rotation land management are under examination to test their resilience - including against pests and diseases.

The Scottish government successfully implements interventions that allow stronger connections between people and food provenance (e.g. local markets). Consumers are willing to pay more for healthy and locally produced food. This continuous support to the arable and horticulture sector helps to deal with major economic and political instability internationally.

Colorado Potato Beetle	Wheat Stem Rust	Blueberry Rust
Moderate effect	Small effect	Permanent effect
<p>The Government has developed a programme to establish precision and target farming, which is adopted by much of the sector, allowing the industry to adapt and mitigate some of the shocks, and allowing strategies to be implemented to protect the sector from stronger shocks.</p> <p>The seed potato industry is the most important part of the industry in Scotland and as the Colorado Potato Beetle is not yet affecting it, its impact is not as problematic as aphid pests.</p> <p>Precision and targeted farming practices would improve early pest and disease detection and allow growers to take action accordingly. This might include easing regulatory rules if necessary. This is also possible because of Brexit.</p>	<p>Continuous R&D allow the sector to adapt and compensates for the low level of responsive actions of farmers in the cereal sector.</p> <p>Wheat is the second most important cereal grown in Scotland although it does not have the importance of barley for the whisky industry.</p> <p>The crop needs high fertiliser inputs. If there are no alternatives and fertiliser allowance is reduced to achieve Net Zero, it is possible that the area planted with wheat will reduce, and the risks of disease outbreak will become lower.</p>	<p>The disease is difficult to control. Consumers' willingness to pay more for blueberries produced in Scotland would have a major impact as costs of production will increase.</p> <p>This would also imply that supermarkets are willing to sell locally produced fruit even though it is not cost competitive compared with other countries like Chile. It depends on the global context and how it affects supply and demand.</p> <p>If other countries become affected by pests/diseases, then this could represent a competitive advantage for Scotland.</p> <p>However, if there is an increase in pest and disease issues in Scotland, then it would reverse the beneficial effects.</p>

Recommendations by Stakeholders

- Quoted: "Do this and do more!" Consider invasive pests and diseases as agricultural support programmes are developed. Incentivise uptake of programme adoption through agricultural policy - relating to CPD / advisory / KE - and possibly through 'conditionality' measures for farmers to receive support payments.
- More R&D about adapting the farming calendar for planting which could potentially help to adapt to the changing climate. Bringing the season forward could potentially help to cope with some of the diseases. Invest in research which helps to understand what measures are needed in addition to other strategies such as relying on husbandry and cultural management.
- Adopting existing solutions in good time, such as detection and application of counter-measures, was mentioned as part of the recommendation to reduce the negative effects of the pests and disease on the sector.
- The economic system was also discussed as being dysfunctional and weak by being based on monoculture and therefore acting as Petri dish for evolution of diseases of all kinds of pests and diseases (when they are not under control). Participants argued that the degree of production being under monoculture was unnecessary. They suggested this system should be changed to a more diverse system growing varieties that have resistance. And they recommended particular mixtures of crop landraces where there is a buffering effect from the genetic diversity that is built into that kind of cropping. This will only happen if new drivers are provided for farmers to shift towards this kind of diversified cropping approach. A shift of production system where farmers grow more food for people rather than for alcohol production or biofuels.
- More R&D in crop diversity and blends was mentioned, highlighting intercropping for instance for potato or blueberry with other crop types to combat pests and diseases such as the blueberry rust.
- Also discussed was the idea of letting the system find its own way of "fighting" pests and diseases by creating more diverse environments. This was seen as opposed to developing research and development in silos, which, although controlling a single pathogen well, can create unanticipated problems or miss targets elsewhere within the system. More research and development on the principle of diversity creating the natural system to provide buffers against potential threats and to understand how best to grow crops under these conditions which are also good for providing nutritionally healthy and economically viable food.

Scenario 3

Scotland as part of ‘feed-the-world’ UK”

International trade is growing again and the arable and horticulture sector in Scotland increasingly produces for export as part of a ‘feed-the-world’ UK. However, Scotland has chosen a more cautious approach to technological change, regarding gene editing, compared with other nations of the UK. This places the Scottish arable and horticulture sector at a disadvantage, especially with regards to England. Scotland increasingly depends on the UK food-supply chain creating a “race-to-the bottom” dynamic regarding standards.

After overcoming major geopolitical tensions, the international system has regained some stability although the global economy still suffers occasional recessionary pressures, and most importantly, governments are very much behind in climate action and their Net Zero targets.

The UK continues to increase its international trade with other countries and increases its economic and political relations globally. Scotland and the UK continue, over 10 years after Brexit, to play an important role in providing crops in the international market. But supply chains are increasingly prone to catastrophic regional and local disruption, resulting from an ever more chaotic climate, and other social and economic events.

Scotland diverges from the rest of the UK in relation to technologies which impact the arable and horticulture sector.

Successive Scottish governments failed to achieve the aim of reducing carbon emissions by 32% reductions by 2032 (as initially established in the 2021 Scotland Climate Smart Agriculture Framework). As a result of continuing with practices that assume a largely predictable and stable climate, the sector is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of pests, pathogens, disease, floods, fires and drought that come with a more chaotic climate, within and across years.

Despite the challenges of climate change, the country exports more crops and significantly increases the economic importance of the drinks industry but less livestock feed is grown. The horticulture sector is less competitive as lack of labour is a continued problem in addition to the technological differences (e.g. gene editing). The horticulture sector is in rapid decline in Scotland but growing in England where the conditions for this sector are better.

The production system is less tolerant of pests and diseases due to changing climate favouring pests and pathogens.

Climate change and international trade bring both opportunities and threats for the agriculture sector. Some technological changes are not allowed in Scotland for instance gene editing, whereas in England these technological advances are allowed and are increasingly being used in agriculture alongside vertical farms, robotics and others technological innovations. Vertical farming in England is becoming established and this creates a divergence between Scotland and the rest of the UK.

In the UK, wealth distribution within the country is polarised, but processed food is affordable for the less well off, although still unhealthy and so imposing significant costs and burdens on the NHS. The country produces more food in response to incentives from international markets. This makes food more affordable but within a production system less tolerant to pests and diseases due to climate change creating more favourable conditions for pests and pathogens. Society is changing and even though meat consumption has declined (more plant proteins are grown in Scotland), biodiversity and carbon emission reduction targets are delayed.

There is an increased reliance of Scotland on the UK food-supply chain with a race-to-the-bottom dynamic regarding food and environmental standards.

Colorado Potato Beetle	Wheat Stem Rust	Blueberry Rust
Moderate effect	Major (long term) effect.	--
Colorado Potato Beetle could have a moderate to major effect under this scenario. The major challenge is the lack of research and development and the technological breach with other nations in the UK. Scotland has an	Under this scenario wheat stem rust has a major effect as wheat is the second most important crop in Scotland for trade and arable land cover.	Under this scenario the main risk is an accelerating decline and disappearance of the fruit sector which could have devastating consequences for rural Scotland and provoke a lack of diversity

<p>important disadvantage for gene editing for developing resistance crop varieties. Contraction of government investment in R&D and capacity is important and could result in increased pest and disease problems because of less investment in chemical and biological pesticides. Given post-Brexit market conditions companies developing these products will not pay for registering a biological pesticide for a very small (i.e. Scottish/UK) market.</p>	<p>Reliance on international trade and crop exports limits the opportunities the changing climatic conditions could bring in terms of growing new crops, thus limiting the possibilities of adapting to the changing weather patterns. Wheat is also used for animal feed; if under this scenario less animal feed is grown this may reduce risks because the area covered by wheat is reduced. Again less investment in R&D will heavily impact the sector.</p>	<p>in production systems (risking the loss of future opportunity of expanding the sector if other fruit producing countries experience challenges or declining production).</p>
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Recommendations by Stakeholders

- More investment in R&D from industry and government is required, bearing in mind the ending of levy-funded AHDB Horticulture. There is a need for policy to address this market failure (in terms of industry investment in R&D).
- Producing more of what we eat. This scenario requires a shift towards a nourish Scotland approach, ensuring that the sector contributes to producing more for local consumption and conversely it requires support to nudge the public to consume more locally grown produce. But, in a more chaotic climate within and across years, farmers will need to hedge their bets – spread risks – which implies more regenerative practices and further adaptations.
- Change in metrics. Develop new metrics as has most recently been endorsed by the FAO. A methodology for rewarding for output based on the number of people and species nourished per unit of output, or area used.
- More recognition is needed of the contribution that grass-roots movements have already made towards developing alternative agro-food systems.
- Building on local connections and local markets “rather than just throwing ourselves” on the very uncertain international trade and an export-oriented economy.
- Implement strategies to protect the sector from stronger shocks by enhancing crop diversity and growing mixtures.

Agriculture elsewhere

The arable and horticulture sector produces almost exclusively for exports creating a polarisation within the industry where only the most profitable farms take advantage of international trade and can invest in technology and innovation. This creates a concentration of production in larger farming operations. There is a strong reliance on food imports and climate change puts Scotland's production at risk, including exports, and pushes for agriculture elsewhere.

After overcoming major geopolitical tensions and a lessening of trade-wars, the international system has regained some stability. Yet the global economy, which is again strongly oriented towards free trade, is subjected to new threats and weaknesses, especially in the face of climate crises.

The UK and Scotland continue to increase their international trade with other countries and strengthen their economic and political relations.

However, this is jeopardized by accelerating climate change. The dominant trend is to favour market-based solutions (i.e. carbon credits etc.) to address climate action, yet results have proven disappointing. This is largely a result of not confronting risk and so it remains largely 'hidden' until something goes wrong, and the Government/taxpayer end up paying while a small number of people profit.

This has direct economic impacts on agriculture in the UK and Scotland. Here, too, policy, practice and markets transfer risk to others so that a small number of people can profit.

The UK and Scotland converge on a common political and economic path.

Net Zero targets remain unreachable as the dominant trend to favour market-based solutions to address climate action has proven to be insufficient. Extreme weather events intensify and are more and more unpredictable, impacting harvests, supply chains and exports.

Successive Scottish governments fail to achieve the aim of reducing carbon emissions by 32% by 2032 (as initially established in the 2021 Scotland Climate Smart Agriculture Framework).

Reduced farm income and less support to the sector reduces investment in technology and science (e.g. using gene editing), increasing uncertainty about new available technologies for most farmers. Only the most profitable farming operations have access to high tech solutions. Technology and information (data) are privatised and only some can access these in the UK. Investment in farm infrastructure is also reduced affecting the possibility to develop knowledge and innovation in agriculture. The catastrophic impacts of climate change are making people realise that there is no easy 'technical' fix out of this and a slow but late dawning realisation that "we have to respect and live within Earth's systems. It's the only planet we have".

Lack of diversity subjects the few crops grown in Scotland to greater vulnerability to pests and diseases. There is a slow realisation that the diversity required for climate resilience is the same as the diversity required for soil health and to sequester greenhouse gases securely into biological systems. And that this is the key to food- fibre- and water- security and hence the rural economy and population health. Risk is foregrounded in policy and practice, guided by: 'how bad could this be'; 'how much does that matter', and 'who pays when it all goes wrong?'

Food is generally affordable for consumers but only thanks to imports, which are increasingly disrupted across supply chains leading to shortages and price volatility. Agricultural production in Scotland is mainly for international markets (e.g Whisky industry) and

production for local food markets is expensive. Some people are beginning to ask questions about a just transition in which Scotland's main contribution to global food security is in alcohol for the benefit of a few – they wonder how this contributes to population health anywhere? On top of the higher dependency from imports, there is a growing two-tier tendency in society, with only the better off being able to afford nutrient-rich fresh, sustainably-produced food, while for most of the population food is largely imported given comparative advantages of overseas food systems, especially for production costs. All of this is highly precarious for all involved as a result of climate risks and price volatility. People ask: is this fair?'

Failure to confront and expose risk leads to Scottish government failing in its efforts to increase awareness about food provenance and the lack of awareness in the population leads to less political pressure for change in food production (such as increasing healthy local food grown sustainably), and there is a decreasing demand for local, Scottish produce. In addition to larger commercial operations, farmers are more likely to move to rewilding, carbon offsetting and provision of leisure activities.

Colorado Potato Beetle	Wheat Stem Rust	Blueberry Rust
Permanent effect	Major to Permanent effect	Major to Permanent effect
<p>Scotland has a premium product and high plant health safeguards in relation to seed and ware potato production. However, the industry would weaken very quickly in this scenario, unless there are crop protection chemicals to defend it against CPB.</p> <p>There are more than ~26 000 ha. of seed and ware potato in Scotland in prime agricultural land, all of which would become fair game to these feeding predators. Without effective controls, then they would become well established. If government wants to stop them getting in, what would they choose? major changes to the whole industry? Prime arable land could no longer be used for potato growing. Would the permanent effect change the entire industry because we would lose all our export markets?</p>	<p>With only 20% of the wheat varieties being resistant to these pathogens and weather being increasingly unpredictable, this pathogen could have a major to permanent effect and further strain the already fragile sector. On one hand weather conditions are favourable to the pathogen and with more land under rewilding the risk of increasing availability of alternative host plants increases the chances for the pest to survive. However, control is possible at early stages. Technology could be applied on large scale cereal farms which are the principal types to be affected. Along the same line, biological controls could represent a viable option if the availability of chemical solutions was a barrier.</p>	<p>Assuming commercial horticulture production survives in this scenario, this pathogen would have major to permanent effects. Investing in technological innovation by businesses would give them the chance to survive; as would pressuring for relaxing regulations on the use of fungicides if the disease becomes established. Because international trade continues the same in this scenario it would be hard for the blueberry sector to continue competing with additional pressures such as this disease.</p>

Recommendations by Stakeholders

- Discussion on recommendations under this scenario was about the reconciliation between available plant protection products (fungicides and pesticides) and existing cropping practices.
- Stakeholders questioned what the costs for the industry would be if these protection products are not available and what the farming best practices should be.
- Conduct a risk analysis on chemical and biological control products available to halt pests and disease and the impact of losing them (or not developing new ones) on the economy of the arable and horticulture sector, rural economy and rural communities. They considered addressing this issue as necessary to avoid restrictions being imposed on the sector similar to the situation experienced by the fishing industry and fishing communities when sustainability quotas restricted fishing activity and economic conditions in that sector.
- Better border controls and inspections of plants and other imported products to reduce the risks of crop losses and costs of treatment which are borne by the businesses. Increase investment in people and for people. Increase support for farmers to monitor fields in relation to pests and diseases.
- Increase resources, and research and development, about chemical substitution for crop protection. Highlighting the fact that pesticides are being banned but few alternatives have been developed yet. Many alternative pesticides have the same chemical properties as previous ones and therefore are being included in the exclusion list.
- Maintaining biodiversity in the fields, agrobiodiversity, intercropping etc. was important for stakeholders specifically for this scenario, as a means to reduce risk of pest and disease establishment. In addition, they recommended schemes that buffer the losses of farmers and insurance schemes which help to buffer crop losses.

- In addition to insurance schemes, there is a need for government guarantee. If government does not want to regulate markets, then they should develop guarantee/assurance schemes for farmers to borrow the money they need to establish their crops and to run the business. In particular, looking at the combination of banks' vulnerability and risks that farming businesses bear. In other words, government assurance schemes should cover the risks that farmers' bank insurance will not cover.

Stakeholders' knowledge elicitation about pests and diseases.

Pest and pathogen threats highlighted by stakeholders. The pest and disease threats identified by stakeholders are summarised in **Table 1**. The reasons given for selecting these pests and pathogens included:

- i) changing climatic conditions (e.g. wetter conditions favouring slug damage and fungal disease incidence; milder winters increasing overwinter persistence of insect pests, including new species from warmer climates);
- ii) appearance of new insect pests (e.g. Colorado beetle) or fungal pathogen strains from overseas or through rapid evolution of new strains locally due to agronomy and climate, resulting in breakdown of crop resistance;
- iii) loss of pesticides;
- iv) changing farming practices (e.g. more trash-borne diseases due to direct drilling; cover crops acting as green bridges between seasons; wildflower strips providing refuge to pests and pathogens); and
- v) new crops or changing crop rotations bringing new pest and disease threats or exacerbating existing threats (e.g. expansion of sugar beet growing could lead to beet nematode increases).

Comparison with pest and pathogen threats identified by modelling. In terms of predicted risk based on proximity to other counties with the pest or pathogen, three of the pests and pathogens noted in Table 1 are listed as present in the UK but not specifically noted in Scotland according to CABI distribution data: mildew, slugs, and Colorado potato beetle, with the latter not yet established in the UK. The English Grain aphid is also known to be present on cereal crops in Scotland. Pests and pathogens predicted to have a high probability of arriving in Scotland ($P_s > 0.24$; Bebber et al., 2024) were not identified by stakeholders. Pests and pathogens with a moderate probability of arriving in Scotland ($P_s > 0.1$; Bebber et al., 2024) and likely to be problematic for major Scottish crops were largely absent from the list selected by stakeholders, although the identification of general threats from aphids and nematodes was detected (c.f. *Diuraphis noxia* and *Meloidogyne javanica*, respectively). In terms of bioclimatic similarity, only cereal aphids and rusts and Colorado potato beetle and potato blight were highlighted by both stakeholders and modelling with many other pests and pathogens identified as potential risks by modelling (Bebber et al., 2024). Blight and Colorado potato beetle were the only threats identified as a trade risk (Bebber et al., 2024) that were also identified by stakeholders, and none of the pest and pathogens predicted to pose a risk through travel were identified by stakeholders.

Table 1. Pest and disease threats anticipated by stakeholders to become more problematic in future Scottish agricultural systems.

Pest or pathogen type	Cereals	Fruit	Potato	Brassicas, legumes & other vegetable crops
Fungal/oomycete pathogens	<i>Septoria</i> (wheat) <i>Rhynchosporium</i> (barley) <i>Ramularia</i> (barley) eyespot (cereals) <i>Gaeumannomyces tritici</i> (take-all of wheat) and <i>Gaeumannomyces avenae</i> (take-all of barley) Rusts Ergot	Mildew <i>Botrytis</i> <i>Monolinia</i> <i>Phytophthora</i> <i>Sclerotinia</i>	Blight	
Arthropod pests	Aphids Leatherjackets	Aphids Spotted wing Drosophila Marmorated stinkbug <i>Xylella</i>	Aphids Colorado potato beetle Wireworms	Cabbage stem flea beetle Pollen beetle Bean weevil Beet nematode Beet moths Cabbage stem weevil Carrot fly
			Potato cyst nematode Other free-living nematodes	
Bacterial pathogens			Zebra Chip Brown rot <i>Pectobacterium</i> Storage diseases	
Viruses			Aphid-vectored viruses (PLRV)	Turnip yellows
Other pests	Slugs Rabbits Pigeons Geese New Zealand flatworm			

Developing strategies and recommendations from Scenarios

Scenario 1

Biocontrol products. This would include enabling regulatory and bureaucratic processes to develop biocontrol products; but also risk analysis (for chemical and biocontrol products) and the impact of losing some (or not developing new ones) on the economy of the arable and horticulture sector.

Consolidation of quality assurance schemes. This would facilitate and consolidate schemes (e.g. Red Tractor, LEAF marque), reducing competition and lessen risk, work, and costs to farmers (if there are fewer available schemes).

Scenario 2

Scheme measures for P&D. This would consider pests and pathogens as part of agricultural programmes and incentivise uptake of control measures through agricultural policy - relating to CPD / advisory / KE - and through 'conditionality' for farmers to receive support payments.

Enable diversified cropping systems. This would create drivers which enable farmers to shift to a more diverse system growing varieties and landraces with genetic diversity though R&D on the principle of diversity and blends (intercropping), creating natural buffering against threats; and to understand how best to grow crops under these conditions which are also good for providing nutritionally healthy and economically viable food.

Scenario 3

Shift towards a "nourish Scotland" approach. This would include creating the conditions to ensure the sector contributes to producing more for local consumption and support to consume more locally grown produce (e.g. schools' procurement, encourage local markets)

Change in metrics. This would develop a new framework for rewarding output based on the number of people and species nourished per unit of output, or area used (as endorsed by the FAO).

Grass-roots movements and proposals. This would recognise the contribution that grass-root movements are already making towards new developments for agri-food system change.

Scenario 4

Protection products and farming practices. This would include increasing understanding about availability of plant protection products (fungicides and pesticides) and what the farming best practices should be, considering the costs to the industry if these protection products are not available.

Import controls. Increase effort for inspecting imported plants/crop products to reduce pest and pathogen import risk and resultant costs to the industry.

Government regulates markets or develops guarantee/assurance schemes. This would allow farmers to borrow the money they need to establish their crops, covering the risks that farmers' bank insurance will not cover.

Further developing these strategies and recommendations we asked stakeholders three additional questions:

- 1) What are your concerns for future pest and disease risks?;
- 2) What further research is needed? (rank in priority order); and
- 3) What is needed to make the arable/horticulture sector more resilient to pests and diseases? (rank in priority order)

1) What are your concerns for future pest and disease risks?

Stakeholders reinforced similar concerns highlighted during the co-design of the scenarios. In addition, they mentioned the need for more emphasis on crop pests and diseases and human health. These comments related to crop diseases in human food crops that affect human health (such as ergot), but also the effects of current agronomic products (such as pesticides), as residues in food could negatively affect human health. In addition, they expressed concerns about the effects of pesticides on the environment.

We presented stakeholders with 5 choices and asked them to rank them responding to “What further research is needed?”. The resulting ranking was as follows:

1. Understanding the implications of changing pest and pathogen management (e.g. chemical to biological control)
2. Co-creation of knowledge for pest and pathogen management
3. Improving decision support to enable targeted control measures
4. Invasion modelling of key pests and pathogens
5. Biophysical and socioeconomic modelling to understand future changes in Scottish agriculture (e.g. novel crops)

Finally, we presented stakeholders with 5 further choices and asked them to rank these answering the question “What is needed to make the arable/horticulture sector more resilient to pests and diseases?”. They ranked these statements in the following order:

1. Diversify crop systems (resistant varieties, intercropping, variety mixtures, adapted rotations etc.).
2. High risk pests and pathogens should be prioritised for early detection and management.
3. Consider emerging pests/pathogens in government agricultural support schemes (monitoring schemes, insurance or assurance schemes).
4. Maintain and publish a list of present and emerging pests and pathogens in Scotland.
5. Maintain and publish data on pest and pathogen interceptions at Scottish entry points.

Summary remarks

The development of the scenarios highlighted several issues which the arable and horticulture sector is facing, and which make it vulnerable to pest and disease threats.

The value of this methodology is to prepare the sector for these future threats and therefore it is important to identify strategies the sector should start to develop as well as recommendations for policy makers and other decision-makers and other stakeholders.

Stakeholders developed recommendations for each scenario, but these recommendations are also relevant for other scenarios. Also, across the scenarios stakeholders consented that **research and development** was crucial for the future of the sector, as was a better understanding of chemical and **biological control products** and the **government enabling** adaptation through various mechanisms such as support schemes, market regulation, changes in metrics and grassroots movements inclusion, and investing in infrastructure.

Diversification, intercropping, increasing varieties of crops and even including silvopastoral systems were mentioned across the workshops. Stakeholders did not reach consensus about diversification: it was viewed positively as a practice to increase resilience to pests and disease; but it was also viewed

negatively as a potential threat to agriculture because it could increase the availability of host plant species as reservoirs for crop pests and pathogens.

Recommendations proposed by stakeholders to mitigate against the pest and disease impacts in future scenarios included greater investment in people involved in farming to improve control and reduce the impact, ensuring fairer market returns to growers to allow investment in (more expensive) production costs and to monitor and reward system performance, consumer education on the impact of their food choices, and access to credit or government assurance schemes to buffer losses and maintain a viable industry.

Three pests and diseases predicted by modelling to become more widespread in Scotland in the future were considered by stakeholders to have moderate, major, or permanent effects on the four future scenarios co-design with stakeholders. The exception was Wheat Stem Rust in the second scenario, which was considered to have a minor effect. A subset of the pests and diseases predicted by modelling to become more problematic to Scottish arable and horticulture production were identified as future threats by stakeholders (aphids, rusts, blight, Colorado potato beetle). Using the three illustrative pest and disease examples allowed participants to recommend actions to mitigate known or anticipated threats; our research did not test for unanticipated threats, which could become increasingly problematic in a more chaotic climate. Reducing the risk of these 'unknown unknown' threats relies on curbing emissions and building resilience into land management systems, aiming to create multiple benefits and managing for multiple risks simultaneously.

Agricultural policy could also allow severe impacts to be mitigated by providing a solid base to develop further some of the recommendations. This includes: the **Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill**, which includes an intention to produce a Code of Practice on Sustainable and Regenerative Agriculture, and the Agricultural Reform programme; **Scotland's Strategic Framework for Biodiversity** (currently under consultation), which includes a commitment to introducing legally binding nature restoration targets; and the **Scottish Good Food Nation Act**, which aims to improve the nation's social and economic wellbeing, the environment, people's health, and economic development. The findings of this research will be communicated to policy stakeholders to inform future policy developments.

References

- Bebber, P., Gurr, S. J., Karley, A. Lozada-Ellison, L., Beale, T. & Gimenez Romero, A. (2024). Interdisciplinary Analysis of Plant Health Threats to Scotland: Project Final Report. PHC2022/05. Scotland's Centre of Expertise for Plant Health (PHC).
- Boden, L. A., Auty, H., Bessell, P., Duckett, D., Liu, J., Kyle, C., McKee, A., Sutherland, L., Reynolds, J., Bronsvort, B., McKendrick, I., (2015) Scenario planning: The future of the cattle and sheep industries in Scotland and their resiliency to disease, *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, Volume 121, Issues 3–4, P. 353-364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2015.08.012>
- Brasier, C.M., (2008). The biosecurity threat to the UK and global environment from international trade in plants. *Plant Pathol.* 57, 792–808. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3059.2008.01886.x>

Chopin, P., Mubaya, C.P., Descheemaeker, K. et al. Avenues for improving farming sustainability assessment with upgraded tools, sustainability framing and indicators. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41, 19 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00674-3>

Cordova-Pozo, K., and Rouwette, E. A. J. A. (2023) Types of scenario planning and their effectiveness: A review of reviews. *Futures*, 149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2023.103153>.

Duckett, D., Currie, M., Elzen, B., Hardy, C., Noble, C., & Townsend, L. (2022). *Comparative Scenario Report: Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas*. DESIRA Consortium. [D3.1 Comparative scenario report.pdf \(gcu.ac.uk\)](#)

Duckett, D., Rivington, M., King, R., Juarez-Bourke, A., Lorenzo-Arribas, A. 'Scenarios for UK Food and Nutrition Security in the wake of the COVID-19 Pandemic' DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4966627

Duong, T. T., Brewer, T. D., Luck, J., & Zander, K. K. (2019). Farmers' assessment of plant biosecurity risk management strategies and influencing factors: A study of smallholder farmers in Australia. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 48(1), 48-57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0030727019829754>

EPIC (2014) "What will the Scottish cattle industry look like in 2040 and how resilient will it be to livestock disease?" <https://www.epicscotland.org/media/1124/epic-cattle-industry-scenario-planning-report.pdf>

Foister, C.E., (1961). *The Economic Plant Diseases of Scotland. A Survey and Check List Covering the Years 1924-1957.* [With Maps.]. H.M. Stationery Office.

Gullino, M.L. (2021). Coffee Rust in Ceylon: Why English People Drink Tea. In: *Spores*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69995-6_5

Han, D., Yoo, D. & Kim, T. (2023). Analysis of social welfare impact of crop pest and disease damages due to climate change: a case study of dried red peppers. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 10, 378 . <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01873-x>

Hasan M. Abdullah, Nusrat T. Mohana *et al.* (2023). Present and future scopes and challenges of plant pest and disease (P&D) monitoring: Remote sensing, image processing, and artificial intelligence perspectives, *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, Volume 32, November 2023, 100996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2023.100996>.

Jones, D.R., Baker, R.H.A., (2007). Introductions of non-native plant pathogens into Great Britain, 1970–2004. *Plant Pathol.* 56, 891–910. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3059.2007.01619.x>

Lozada, Luz Maria, & Karley, Alison Jane. (2023). What will affect future Scottish arable and horticulture production? Identifying drivers of change with agricultural stakeholders. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7810017>

McCook, S., (2006). Global rust belt: *Hemileia vastatrix* and the ecological integration of world coffee production since 1850. *J. Glob. Hist.* 1, 177–195. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S174002280600012X>

O'Rourke, K. (1994). The Economic Impact of the Famine in the Short and Long Run. *The American Economic Review*, 84(2), 309–313. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2117849>

Plant Health Centre (2024), Agriculture. Available at: [Agriculture | Plant Health Centre](#) (Accessed 1 April 2024).

Scottish Government, (2021) A New Blueprint for Scotland's Arable Sector. The Arable Climate Change Group. URL [A New Blueprint For Scotlands Arable Sector \(www.gov.scot\)](#) (Accessed 10 Nov 2023)

Scottish Government, (2023). Results from the Scottish Agricultural Census: June 2023 [WWW Document]. URL <http://www.gov.scot/publications/results-scottish-agricultural-census-june-2023/> (accessed 12.12.23).

Wenzlhuemer, R. (2008). From Coffee to Tea Cultivation in Ceylon, 1880–1900: An Economic and Social History. Leiden: Brill, 2008